

Evaluation of IR experiments

Cranfield 1 test

1. Background

The primary extensive assessment of information retrieval systems took place at Cranfield, UK, beneath the supervision of C W Cleverdon, and is known as the Cranfield 1 project. The primary Cranfield study started in 1957 and was reported by Cleverdon in 1962.

2. Scope of the project

The project was planned to compare the effectiveness of four indexing frameworks,

- An alphabetical subject catalogue based on a subject heading list.
- A UDC classified catalogue with alphabetical chain index to the class headings developed.
- A catalogue based on a faceted classification and an alphabetical index to the class headings.
- A catalogue compiled by the Uniterm coordinate index.

3. Methodology

The study included 18,000 indexed items and 1200 search topics. The reports, half of which were research reports and half periodical articles, were chosen equally from the general field of aeronautics and the specialized field of high-speed aerodynamics. Then three indexes were chosen – one with subject information, one with indexing experience and one straight from library school having neither subject foundation nor indexing experience. Each indexer was inquired to index each source record five times, investing 2, 4, 8, 12 and 16 minutes per record. One hundred source records in this way gave rise to a set of 6000 indexed items (100 documents X 3 indexers X 4 frameworks X 5 times). Each of these 6000 items was tested in three places, and thus the framework worked on altogether 18,000 (6000 X 3 phases) indexed items. The test was taken in three stages with a view to discover whether the level of performance expanded with expanding experience of the system personnel.

3. Results and Significance

The results of the Cranfield 1 test negated the common belief with respect to the nature of information retrieval system in numerous ways. The test proved that the performance of a system does not depend on the experience and subject foundation of the indexer. It appeared that systems where reports are organized by faceted classification scheme perform ineffectively in comparison to the alphabetical list and uniterm system. It identified the major factors that influence the performance of retrieval systems, and developed for the first time the methodologies that might be applied effectively in assessing information retrieval systems. In addition, it showed that recall and precision is the two most important parameters for deciding the performance of information retrieval systems and that these two parameters are related contrarily to each other.

The following discoveries of Cranfield are noteworthy

- Indexing times over 4 minutes gave no genuine enhancement in performance

- A high quality of indexing might be obtained from non-technical indexers
- The system worked at a recall rate of 70-90% and precision rate of 8 – 20%
- A 1 % improvement in precision could be accomplished at the cost of 3% loss in recall
- Recall and precision were contrarily related to each other
- All four indexing strategies gave a broadly similar performance.

4. Limitations

Cranfield 1 was the most noteworthy study within the decade of 1958-68. Indeed at that point it was not free from criticisms. One of the most criticisms against this study was the artificiality without much relation to the real-life situation. The questions used for the test were 'manufactured' from the source documents. It was argued by the critics that to utilize an editorial as a source report for framing a question and then to report the results of search for the same document in response to the same question is exceptionally artificial. In a real-life circumstance queries are not based on past information of availability of the document within the store. Another criticism was that this test identified the level of performance of the indexing systems concerned, but it did not throw any light on reasons for disappointment of these systems. In truth these questions were taken into consideration within the second Cranfield test.

Cranfield test 2

1. Background

The disadvantages of Cranfield required the conduct of advance studies. The second stage of Cranfield studies, known as Cranfield 2, started in 1963 and completed in 1966. The Cranfield 2 was a controlled test that endeavored to examine the components of index languages and their impact on the performance of retrieval systems. In Cranfield 2, the various index language devices were assessed in terms of their impact on the recall and precision of a retrieval system.

2. Scope of the project

This study tried to examine the impact by varying each factor, while keeping the other factors constant. Some of the disadvantages of Cranfield I were mechanisms between the indexers and users.

3. Methodology

The second Cranfield test was a controlled experiment that endeavored to survey the effects of the components of index languages on the performance of retrieval systems. This study attempted to evaluate the impact by changing each factor, whereas keeping the others steady. Altogether 29 index languages formed by the combination of concepts were tried on 1400 documents. The test was conducted on a collection of 1400 reports and articles collected from the field of high speed

aerodynamics and aircraft structures.

The documents were indexed in three distinctive ways:

- a) Each document was examined and critical concepts were chosen and recorded in a normal language;
- b) Concepts signified by the single words were recorded; and
- c) Concepts with a weighting (extending from 1 to 3) were combined to represent the subject contents of the documents. Five different sorts of indexing languages with varieties were utilized in this study:

- * Single term index language with 8 varieties like uncontrolled natural dialect, controlled equivalent words, controlled word form, etc.;
- * Simple concept index language with 15 varieties by applying different controls;
- * Controlled term index language with 6 similar varieties;
- * Title index with two varieties; and
- * Index language created from abstracts with 2 varieties.

In this way, 33 index languages were shaped in this study by distinctive levels of coordination of index terms. To conduct searches 221 questions created by the creators of the research papers were used. Significance of each document was ascertained for the questions by grading them from 1 to 4 in the following way:

- 1) Complete answer to the question;
- 2) High degree of relevance;
- 3) Valuable, giving general background of the work or dealing with a specific area; and
- 4) Minimum interest, giving information like historical perspective.

For the evaluation, a single performance measure; called normalised recall, was introduced. This is a ratio of cumulated recall ratio and number of search stages involving document cut-off groups.

4. Results and significance

The results of Cranfield 2 were rather unexpected because, other than corroborating inverse relationships of recall and precision, the results appeared that:

- 1) A best performance result was obtained by the use of natural language single term index, such as Uniterm, based on words happening in document texts;
- 2) With the natural language formation of groups or classes of terms beyond the stage of true equivalent words or word forms resulted in fall of efficiency;
- 3) Use of precision gadgets like partitioning or intermixing was not as effective as the fundamental accuracy of coordination;
- 4) It was recommended that the terms taken from documents may be utilized effectively with minimum control in a post-coordinate index and it is helpful to eliminate equivalent words. But any measures taken to control the vocabulary

are likely to decrease its efficiency;

5) In the case where concepts were utilized for ordering, the system performance declined with the introduction of superordinate, subordinate, and collateral classes in conjunction with the first concepts;

6) When broader and narrower terms were included along with the controlled languages of the thesaurus, the execution worsened; and

7) Index languages shaped out of titles performed way better than those shaped out of abstracts.

5. Limitations

The results of the Cranfield 2 tests were unexpected because the test performing index languages were composed of uncontrolled single words happening in records. In any case, the variables utilized in the study were subject to criticisms. Each index language comprised of distinctive units of words, expressions, or combinations of both. Both the documents and queries were shaped in the same way. Thus, the matching of questions to documents would assess the relative effectiveness of the languages of different specificity. Vickery comments that the measures utilized in the second Cranfield project don't satisfactorily characterise those aspects of retrieval performance, those are of operational importance.

Medlars

1. Background

Performance of the Medical Literature Analysis and Retrieval System (MEDLARS) of the US National Library of Medicine was surveyed during August 1966 to July 1967. The test was conducted on the operational database of MEDLARS, a database of biomedical articles, index entries being drawn from the Mesh.

2. Scope of the project

The purpose of the MEDLARS test was to assess the existing MEDLARS framework and to discover the ways for improvisation. The document collection available on the MEDLARS service at the time of the test comprised of about 7,00,00 things.

3. Methodology

21 user groups were chosen from the user community that would -

- supply a few test questions;
- cover all sorts of subjects in the requests; and
- cover all categories of users.

The user group so selected provided 302 search requests. Each query was formulated in terms of Mesh by the system administrator and searches were conducted. After

completion of a search the sample yield was sent to the clients for relevant assessment. Photocopies of the articles, rather than simple reference, were supplied for the relevance evaluation. The user was asked to mark each retrieved item utilizing the following scales:

H1 – of major value;

H2 – of minor value;

W1 – of no value;

W2 – value unknown.

Precision of the searches were calculated from these figures with the following equation:

$$\text{Precision ratio} = ((H1 + H2)/L) \times 100$$

(Where L is the number of sample things retrieved)

4. Result and significance

The average number of references recovered for each search was 175, with an average or overall precision ratio of 50.4%; i.e. of the average 175 references retrieved, about 87 were found to be not significant. The overall recall ratio was 57.7% as calculated by an indirect method. Taking the average search, and assuming that approximately 88 of the references found were pertinent, with an overall recall ratio of 57.7% implies that about 150 references ought to have been found, but 62 were missed. However, the recall and precision ratios for each of the 302 searches were analysed and individual ratios were then averaged in the MEDLARS test. The results were:

Recall ratio

Overall

57.7%

50.4%

Major value

65.2%

Precision ratio 25.7%

An elaborate analysis of retrieval failures revealed that over the 302 searches, there were 797 recall failures and 3038 precision failure. The results of the MEDLARS test driven to a series of recommendations for the improvement of the MEDLARS performance:

A few eminent changes made to

the MEDLARS as a result of this test incorporate design of a new search request form (intended to ensure that a request statement is a good reflection of the information need behind it); and expansion of the entry vocabulary and improvement of its accessibility, and the adoption of an increased level of integration among personnel involved in indexing, searching and vocabulary control devices.

5. Limitations

The two most basic problems confronted in the assessment of Medlars were ensuring that the body of the test request was as far as possible representative of the total spectrum of demands processed. Another is that establishing methods for determining recall and precision performance.

SMART Retrieval experiment

1. Background

The SMART System was designed in 1964, as an experimental tool for the evaluation of the effectiveness of different types of analysis and search procedures

2. Scope of the project

It is used to

- take documents and search queries posed in English;
- perform a fully automatic content analysis of texts;
- match analyzed search statements and contents of documents;
- Retrieve the stored items which are similar to the queries.

3. Methodology

A number of methods were adopted for automatic content analysis of documents, like –

- Word suffix cut-off methods;
- Thesaurus look-up procedures;
- phrase generation methods;
- Statistical term associations;
- Hierarchical term expansion; etc.

4. Result and significance

The following evaluation measures were generated by the SMART System:

- A recall – precision graph showing the average precision value at ten discrete recall points - from a recall of 0.1 to a recall of 1.0 in intervals of 0.1.
- Two global measures- normalized recall and normalized precision, which together reflect the overall performance of the system.
- Two simplified global measures, known as rank recall and log precision, respectively.

It was observed that the SMART evaluation output did not vary with the variations in the relevance judgments. The recall-precision output was basically invariant for the collection under study. It was concluded that if the relevance assessments by the query authors are typical of what can be expected from the general user populations, then the resulting average recall-precision figures appear to be stable indicators of system performance which do in fact reflect actual retrieval effectiveness'.

TREC experiment

1. Background

In 1991, the US Defence Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA), funded the TREC tests, to be run by the National Institute of Science and Technology (NIST) in order to enable information retrieval analysts to scale up from small collections of data to bigger experiments. TREC is a yearly workshop series aimed at building the infrastructure required for extracting pertinent data from expansive volumes of electronic records. The primary TREC Conference was held in 1992 and investigate into improved text-retrieval techniques has proceeded ever since. The archive collection of TREC is known as the TIPSTER collection. TIPSTER reflects the diversity of subject matter, word choice, scholarly fashion, formats etc. Its essential collection is in gigabytes with over a million records.

2. Scope of the project

The objectives of the TREC experiments have been to

- Support retrieval research based upon large test collections.
- Increase communication among industry, academia and government.
- Enhance the transfer of technology from research labs to commercial items.
- Enhance the availability of proper evaluation techniques for use by industry and academia.

3. Methodology

Topic statements (i.e. query statements), which may be either completely automatic or absolutely manual or blended, were made by the same individual who performed the relevance assessment for that topic. Assessors came to NIST with their ideas for topics, searched the document collection and finally evaluated the number of relevant documents per topic. Significance judgments in TREC were based on twofold decision- whether a document was relevant or not. Identifying all the relevant documents against a specific query from a collection of around a million records for estimating recall was logically absurd. Hence, relative recall instead of absolute recall for each query was calculated. In calculating relative recall, 100 top-ranking pertinent documents for' each system and for each query were combined together to produce a 'pool' of pertinent documents. At that point, each system's retrieved documents for a query or topic were compared with these important records. The proportion of the 'pool' of important documents that a single system retrieved for a query or topic is relative recall. Yield lists of 100 top-ranking records from each participating research group were sent to NIST where the 100 top-ranking documents for each topic from all the participating research groups were consolidated into a single set and then given over to the assessor for pertinent evaluation.' Most of the relevant documents were found by pooling all the results from all the participating groups. The results for each

framework was then analyzed to create different performance measures.

4. Result and significance

- i) Utilize of pooling to deliver the sample results for relevance judgements was found to be more than adequate for test collection.
- ii) Automatic development of queries from natural language queries appears to work well, or superior than, manual development of queries, which is encouraging for groups supporting the use of simple natural language interfaces for retrieval systems.
- iii) Noteworthy improvement of retrieval performance over TREC 1 was observed in TREC 2 in regard of the routing task with the increase of documents per topic (200 per topic to 1000) and database size (1 gigabyte to 3 gigabytes);
- iv) Level of performance was same in spite of differences experimental designs. For examples: some groups created queries automatically from the topic statements while others generated the queries manually; relevance feedback was not incorporated in numerous systems; the computer platform used extended from PCs to a supercomputer.
- v) Contrasts in precision-recall curve was negligible; and
- vi) In spite of the fact that the precision-recall results were similar, there was a large scatter within the actual documents retrieved.

5. Limitations

The main criticism against TREC centers around the methodological issues. TREC tests were carried out within the conventional laboratory paradigm, which is exceptionally troublesome to relate to users browsing information on the Web as opposed to traditional library setting.

STAIRS Test

Background

In 1985, Blair and Maron (1985) published a report on a large-scale experiment aimed at assessing the retrieval effectiveness of a full-text search and retrieval system. This is known as STAIRS (Storage and Information Retrieval System) Study.

Scope of the project

The database examined in the STAIRS study comprised of about 40,000 documents, speaking to roughly 350,000 pages of hard copy text utilized in the defence of a large corporate lawsuit. One important feature of STAIRS was that the lawyers who were to use the system for litigation support stipulated that they must be able to retrieve 75% of all the documents relevant to a given request. The major objective of the STAIRS evaluation was to assess how well the system could retrieve all the documents (and only

those) pertinent to a given request and measures of recall and precision were used for this purpose.

Methodology

In STAIRS Project, precision was calculated by separating the total number of 'vital', 'satisfactory', and 'marginally relevant' documents by the total number of documents retrieved. For the calculation of recall, a sampling technique was adopted. Random samples were taken and these were assessed by the lawyers. The total number of relevant documents that existed in these subsets was evaluated.

Results

Out of the 51 requests, values for recall and precision were calculated for 40 and the remaining 11 were utilized to check the sampling strategies and control for possible inclination within the assessment of retrieved and sample tests. The value of precision extended in percentage terms from 100%. In attempting to discover out why STAIRS could retrieve only one out of five pertinent items in reaction to a request, they point out that a retrieved set of several thousand documents is impractical to browse on the part of the user, and quit naturally the client in such cases wants to reformulate the query by adding more and more search terms to bring the output size to a manageable limit.

Limitations

One of the reasons for the failure of STAIRS was, "It was impossibly difficult for users to predict the exact words, their combinations and phrases used in all or most of the relevant documents and only in those documents.

References

- Harman, Donna. (2011). Information Retrieval Evaluation. 10.2200/S00368ED1V01Y201105ICR019.
- Information Retrieval Experiment, chapter 4, pages 44–58. Butterworths, 1981.
- Lancaster, F. W. Information Retrieval Systems: Characteristics, Testing, and Evaluation, Wiley, New York (1968)
- N. J. Belkin. Ineffable concepts in information retrieval. In K. Sparck Jones, editor, "Robertson, s. E. A Theoretical Model of the Retrieval Characteristics of Information Retrieval Systems, Ph.D. Thesis, University of London (1976).
- Robertson, S.E. and Beaulieu, M. (1997), "Research and evaluation in information retrieval", Journal of Documentation, Vol. 53 No. 1, pp. 51-57.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/EUM0000000007190>
- Salton, G. (Ed.) The SMART Retrieval System: Experiments in Automatic Document Processing, Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs, N. J. (1971)
- Sanderson, Mark. (2010). Test Collection Based Evaluation of Information Retrieval Systems. Foundations and Trends in Information Retrieval. 4. 247-375. 10.1561/1500000009.

Sparck Jones, K. and Van Rijsbergen, c. J. Information retrieval test collections, *Journal of Documentation* 32, 59-75 (1976)